

Identification of non volatile migrant compounds and NIAS in polypropylene films used as food packaging characterized by UPLC-MS/QTOF.

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Abstract

Migration of non volatile compounds from twenty six PP films used as food contact materials has been studied in four simulants (ethanol 95% and 10%, acetic acid 3% and Tenax ®) and analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF. Seventy six compounds have been identified, where 76% of them were NIAS coming from degradation of additives used, such as methyl or ethyl or hexyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) from Irganox 1076 and Irganox 1010 degradation; or impurities such as N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) amines, or compounds of unknown origin, like hydro-ceramides. The most common compounds found were glyceryl monostearate or monopalmitate, erucamide, irganox 1010, irgafos 168, irgafos 168 OXO, N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) tridecylamine and N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) pentadecylamine.

Six films didn't comply with the European Regulation N° 10/2011/EU, where Irganox 1010 and the group of N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) amines exceeded their SMLs. Other films surpassed the maximum concentration recommended by Cramer for the compounds of class II (degradation products) or III (amide compounds) when ethanol 95% was used as simulant.

1. Introduction

Polypropylene is a widely used material to manufacture films and containers for food packaging. Among its main characteristics the following ones can be highlighted: its

optimum cost/benefit ratio, versatility in its uses, good processability, lightness, moisture barrier, organoleptic and chemical properties, thermal and rupture resistance and transparency [1].

There is a lot of bibliography about the use of PP to package different types of food like biscuits, bread, candy, snackfoods and dried foods mainly [2, 3]. Or more specific applications such as quince jelly, cheese [3], pasta [4], screw cap for fruit juices [5] or soda, meat or fish can cover [6], or also for utensils used for food [7]. Recently, PP has been also used as alternative to polycarbonate for baby bottles [8-11] due to the problems with the migration of Bisphenol A from this material.

Nowadays, there is a great concern and compromise from companies and industry manufactured of these plastics, about the study of potential migrants. Within these components susceptible to migrate; monomers, additives, catalyst and degradation products could be found. To guarantee their safety, the materials must fulfill the European Regulation N° 1935/2004 [12] about materials and articles into contact with food and also European Regulation N° 10/2011/EU [13] where the positive list of monomer, starting substances and additives authorized and their specific migration limits (SML), as well as, the conditions (time, temperature and simulants) for migration tests are established.

Two different types of methodologies (target or non-target analysis) have been used for the study of these potential migrants in PP. Target analysis is usually applied to look for known migrated substance, usually to those intentionally added substances (IAS) or to some well known non-intentionally added substances (NIAS). For example, migration of antioxidants commonly used such as BHT [14], irganox 1010 [15] and irgafos 168 [16, 17] in different conditions, including the microwave heating or high-pressure processing [18]. Or also, light stabilizers like Chimassorb 944, 81 and different types of Tinuvin [19-21]. These analyses were carried out by GC-MS and HPLC-MS for volatile and non volatile compounds respectively. Other important migrants determined were mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH), and polyolefin oligomeric saturated hydrocarbons (POSH) by a comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography (GCxGC) [4, 22, 23].

Non- target analysis is a tedious and difficult task, where the first aim is basically to identify any chemical compound present in the migrant sample by a screening assay.

There are several studies about non target analysis from PP, especially for volatile compounds. Several NIAS were detected in baby bottles [10, 11, 24], in films, laminate or granulate PP [5, 6, 25-28], like different types of phthalates, alkanes, degradation products such as 7,9-di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione, methyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propionate, 3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde or 3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone, among others, were found. All these compounds were analyzed and identified by GC-MS assisted by NIST or WYLEY library. However, few works based on the combination of GC coupled to time-of flight mass analyzer (MS/QTOF) for PP samples were found [29-31]. This mass analyzer is considered the best choice for non target analysis, due to its high capacity of performing accurate mass measurements and good sensitivity in full scan, increasing the identification efficiency. The high resolution MS provide the accurate MS, which is the essential tool to identify non volatile compounds, as a library of MS spectra is not available for these compounds, although NIST Peptide MS Library, EPA Tandem Mass Spectrometry and NIST 17 Tandem MS Library have been developed [32]

Much less bibliography was found about non target analysis for non volatile compounds from PP samples [24, 30, 31, 33]. Only few compounds were identified, for example N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl)tridecylamine as a NIAS, or an optical brightening agent, 2,5-bis(5'-tert-butyl-2-benzoxaolyl) thiophene. This work was focused on non-target study of migration of non-volatile compounds from a wide number of PP samples from different manufacturing companies. The main purpose was to increase the knowledge of possible NIAS that could appear, and so, to give a complete overview of all compounds that could come from this type of plastic. This study was carried out by UPLC-MS/QTOF as a powerful tool for this type of analysis[34-37].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

The standards triallyl pentaerythritol (1471-17-6), NX 8000 (882073-43-0) , trihexyl trimellitate (1528-49-0), tinosorb OMC (5466-77-3), oleamide (301-02-0), chimassorb

81 (1843-05-6), glyceryl monostearate (31566-31-1), dinonyl phthalate (84-76-4), irganox 3114 (27676-62-6), diisodecyl phthalate (26761-40-0), irganox 1010 (6683-19-8), erucamide (112-84-5), irganox 1076 (2082-79-3), irgafos 168 (31570-04-4), palmitic acid (57-10-3), stearic acid (57-11-4), 3,5-Di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1620-98-0), methyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoate (6386-38-5), benzenepropanoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- (20170-32-5), Glyceryl dihexadecanoate (26657-95-4), N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) dodecylamine (1541-67-9), Octadecanamide, N,N'-1,2-ethanediylbis- (110-30-5), Octadecanamide (124-26-5), 13-Docosanamide,N-hydroxy-, (13Z)- (119042-56-7), 11-Eicosanamide, (11Z)- (10436-08-5) tetradecanamide (638-58-4), hexadecanamide (629-54-9), 9-Octadecanamide, (9Z) (301-02-0), 3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1620-98-0), hexamide (628-02-4), 2,6-di-tert-butyl-4-(1-methylpropyl)-phenol (17540-75-9), formic acid, acetic acid and tetrahydrofuran were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Química S.A (Madrid, Spain). All were of analytical quality. Ethanol, water and methanol of HPLC grade were supplied by Scharlau Chemie S.A (Sentmenat, Spain). Tenax TA 80/100 mesh was supplied by Supelco (Bellefonte, USA).

2.2. Market samples

Migration from twenty six different types of PP intended for food contact materials was studied. All materials were supplied by different European companies in order to have a representative sampling of PP used in the EU market to package different types the food.

None information about their formulations was supplied due to confidentiality reasons. Only, the final intended of these materials was known, what means, the type of food intended to be in contact with them.

The materials under study are shown in Table 1.

2.3. Migration assays

The migration assays were carried out with four different simulants according to Commission Regulation 10/2011/EU [13]. For each material, the simulants tested were chosen depending on their final uses according to the intended food

Ethanol 10% (simulant A) and acetic acid 3 % (simulant B) were selected when the plastics were intended for hydrophilic food character. Ethanol 95 % (simulant D) and Tenax ® (simulant E) were selected for fat and dry foods respectively [13].

The simulants chosen for each sample and the final use of these materials in the market are shown in the Table 1.

The migration tests were performed by immersion of the plastics in the liquid simulants (A, B or/and E), following the proportions established in the 10/2011/EU [13] legislation ($6\text{dm}^2 / 1 \text{Kg}$ simulant). And then, the assay was kept in an oven at 60°C for 10 days. All samples were monomaterial and monolayer PP.

For migration experiments with Tenax ® as food simulant, 2×4 cm cut-outs of PP under study were full covered with 0.32 grams of Tenax® forming a uniform layer ($4 \text{g}_{\text{Tenax}}/\text{dm}^2$) according to UNE-EN-14338 [38]. Then, they were placed over an aluminum foil and inside a Petri dish and kept in the oven at 60°C during 10 days. After this period, Tenax® was extracted two consecutive times with 3 mL of ethanol [35, 36]. Previously, Tenax was purified by Soxhlet extraction with acetone and ethanol during 6 hours and further dried in the oven at 100°C

After that, A and B simulants were directly analyzed by UPLC-MS-QTOF. However, D and E simulants were previously concentrated $\times 6$ under a gentle stream of N_2 and analyzed by the same methodology subsequently described.

2.3. UPLC- MS/QTOF analysis.

Chromatography was carried out in an Acquity™ system couple to Xevo G2 QTOF as detector, both supplied by Waters (Milford, MA, USA). The detector consisted of an API source (atmospheric pressure ionization) with an electrospray interface (ESI) coupled to a Xevo G2 mass spectrometer with a hexapole, a quadrupole, a collision cell and a time of flight as analyzer (QTOF).

For chromatographic separation an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column of 17 μm particle size (2.1 mm x 100 mm) also from Waters (Milford, MA, USA) was used. The solvents used as mobile phase were water (phase A) and methanol (phase B), with or without 0.1 % formic acid for positive and negative ionization, respectively. The column flow was 0.3 mL/min and the column temperature was 35°C. The gradient used was 98-2% phase A - phase B finishing at 100% phase B after of 15 min. The volume of sample injected was 5 μL .

Instrumental parameters were as follows: the electrospray probe was used in positive (ESI+) and negative (ESI-) modes and in sensitivity mode. The mass range considered was from 10 to 1000 Da. The corona voltage was 2.5 kV for (ESI+) and 0.5 kV for (ESI-). Two cone voltages were used for each injection: 30 and 75V, in order to obtain a greater number of compounds detected. The source temperature was 150° C, the desolvation gas temperature 450°C and the desolvation gas flow 650Lh⁻¹.

MS^E mode was selected for the acquisition, which alternates between two functions: function 1 acquiring at low-energy to obtain the exact mass precursor ion spectra and function 2 acquiring at elevated-energy exact mass fragment ions. The collision ramp energy was from 15 to 40 V.

MassLynx v.4.1 software (Waters, Milford MA, USA) was used to analyze the samples and ChromaLynx (Waters, Milford MA, USA) was used to deconvolute the spectra.

2.4. Identification of migrant compounds from plastics.

The first step for the identification was to determine which chromatographic peaks came from the sample. For this purpose, a previous visual comparison between the migration chromatograms of each sample with their respective blanks of simulants was carried out. The different peaks found were called “markers”. In addition, to complete the number of “markers” for each sample, a Chromalynx XS ® software tool was used. This is capable to find different peaks which appear in the sample and not in the blank, even though they are not visually detected. The parameters selected for Chromalynx XS software tool from Waters were: non targeted analysis, mass tolerance ± 20 mDa, retention time ± 0.2 min and ions abundance above 1000.

After this step, a list the “markers” was obtained for all plastics under study. Each marker was defined by its retention time and its precursor ion with its exact mass.

Subsequently, the identification of the “markers” was carried out. Then, the elemental composition was determined, assisted by the Elemental Composition tool within MassLynx 4.1. This software provides the most probable formula for each precursor ion, considering that the molecules are formed with the most common elements (C, H, O, N, Cl, S, P and Na as adduct) selected by the analyst. Once the different options of the elemental composition were known, the molecular structures were searched in chemical databases such as Chemspider [www.chemspider.com] or Scifinder [scifinder.cas.org] obtaining a number of candidates. The selection of these candidates was made according to chemical criteria based on knowledge of the polymers and its possible additives as well as on the experience

Finally, to confirm the “marker” compounds, Mass Fragment ® software was utilized. This tool compare the spectra of our candidates above selected, with the unknown compounds, both fragmented by function 2 (high energy) of MS^E. If their fragments coincided, the identification was given as “very probable”

When the pure standards were commercially available, this identification was confirmed, comparing the retention time and mass spectra to the “marker”.

2.5. Quantification of migrant compounds from PP films

For the quantification, calibration curves were prepared using the pure standard solutions in ethanol. If the standard was not available, the quantification was carried out with a standard of similar molecular structure. These were analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF with the methodology above described. Three replicates of each concentration level were analyzed to determine the reproducibility.

For A, B and D2 simulants, the concentration of migrant compounds was expressed as milligrams of compounds per Kilogram simulant.

To calculate the migration values for Tenax as solid simulant in mg/Kg, the absolute mass migrating in mg was calculated. This value was divided by the 0.08 dm² used in the migration test and the ratio 6dm² / 1Kg of simulant (regulation 10/2011/EU) [13].

2.6. Risk assessment.

Risk assessment of the identified migrant compounds was applied. First, the migrants were searched in the positive list of the legislation 10/2011/EU [13], and the values found were compared their specific migration limits (SML). For those non listed compounds, the TTC (Cramer's list) (software Toxtree®) was applied in order to classify its toxicity. Cramer classifies the compounds according to their chemical structures into three categories (From class I, low toxicity to class III, high toxicity)

And recommends maximum values of human exposure for each toxicity class [39]. The values of estimated daily intake (EDI) for class I, II and III are 1.8, 0.54 and 0.09 mg per person per day, respectively. According to the European rules [13, 40], the worst possible scenario of intake is that, an adult consumes every days 1 Kg food packaged in 1 dm³. Therefore, the maximum migration recommended for each class is I, II and III, 1.8; 0.54 and 0.09 mg/Kg respectively.

3. Results and Discussion.

Migration from twenty six different films based on PP was evaluated in this work. These samples were used to package different types of food like fresh meat, fish, pizza, cheese, nuts, biscuits, fried potatoes, chocolate, coffee, different types of sauces... They were supplied by different European plastic companies in order to obtain a representative sampling of these materials that can be present in the market for food package contact.

Firstly, the migration of these materials was carried out in different simulants depending on their intended use. After that, these were analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF with their corresponding control analysis. Then, untarget analysis was carried out to detect and identify the migrants from these plastics. This complex and tedious work was necessary

due to the lack of knowledge of their compositions and also, the possibility of finding new compounds from degradation, reaction by products or impurities (NIAS).

After the identification, the migrant compounds were quantified and then, the risk assessment was applied following the above mentioned procedure.

3.1. Identification of migrants from PP films.

The simulants, after migration test, were analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF in order to identify non volatile migrant compounds from these PP films studied

Two migration chromatograms from PP18 sample to ethanol 95% and its respective blank are shown in the Figure 1. Fifteen migrated compounds were detected which don't appear in the blank. They were highlighted with numbers and detailed in Table 2.

All migrated compounds detected in all samples and simulants studied are organized by their retention times in table 2. Their molecular masses, MS fragments and their molecular formula are also shown.

A total of seventy four compounds were found including known additives and also NIAS. Some of these NIAS seemed to have their origin in these additives due to their similar structures.

3.1.1 Migrant additives in PP samples.

The first part of Table 2 (compounds 1-16) lists the compounds commercially used for the manufacture of polymers (which had brand names), whose functions are as antioxidants, such as irganox 1010 and 1076, irgafos 168, chimassorb 81 and irganox 3114 also used as polymer stabilizer. Besides, several plasticizers were found like trihexyl trimellitate, dioctyl and diisodecyl phthalate. Some slip agents as erucamide or oleamide and clarified agent like NX 8000. Also a surfactant, emulsifier and UV absorber like glyceryl monostearate and tinosorb OMC respectively. And also, palmitic and stearic acid as lubricants [6, 10, 11, 28, 41, 42].

3.1.2 Migrant unknown compounds in PP samples.

The second part of this table (compound numbers 17-74), was completed with the unknown compounds (NIAS), which have been organized and grouped by different families as follows:

3.1.2.1. Family 1: Family formed with reference structure

Family 1 (Table 2, compounds from 17 to 26) was formed by the compounds that had a similar structure constituted by a group 3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl (C₁₄H₂₂O), which was assigned the name of “reference structure” and it is shown in Table 3.

Inside this group, the compounds 17 and 18 (Table 2) had the reference structure bonded to an aldehyde group. The mass difference between both compounds was 14.0159 m/z that corresponded to the gain of CH₂ (both compounds shown in Table 3). Their identifications were corroborated by the availability of the 3,5-Di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (compound 17) as standard. Their main mass fragments in both compounds were [MH⁺]- 56.0624 m/z by the lost of C₄H₈ and the mass 57.0704 m/z. Both compounds were found in bibliography as degradation products derived from phenolic antioxidants [5, 10, 43, 44].

The rest of molecules of this family 1 (19-26) formed Na adducts and all of them had the “reference structure” above named bonded with a propanoate group. This new system called “structure of repetition” is also shown in Table 3. It must be emphasized that this structure was also common in the antioxidants Irganox 1076 and Irganox 1010 (Table 3) above described.

In some of these new compounds, this “structure of repetition” was bonded for example to a methyl, ethyl (gain of CH₂) or hexyl (gain of C₅H₁₀) (Table 2 and Table 3; compounds number 19, 20 and 21 respectively). Only the compound number 19 (methyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)) was corroborated by its retention time and its mass spectrum with its standard commercially available. The rest of molecules had the same fragmentation pattern with the accurate common masses like 259.1410, 219.1752 and 107.0487, m/z.

Figure 2 shows the spectrum of fragmentation of methyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl), with their fragmented structures according to Mass Fragment tools.

These NIAS compounds detected may come from degradation of Irganox 1076 or Irganox 1010 fragmenting their ester chains by different parts [10, 25, 26, 31, 41].

Among the compounds 23, 24, 25 and 26 shown in table 3 only the compound number 23 could be corroborated with its standard. The rest of these compounds were identified by Mass fragment tools obtaining the same fragmentation pattern with the common mass 317.1429 m/z and the mass $[MNa^+]-39.9925$ m/z (by the lost of Na adduct and OH)

These last compounds seemed to be degradation products from Irganox 1010 fragmented by different parts. Their structures showed a clear relationship, where the oxygen of ester was bonded to hydrogen forming an O-H bond and producing the rupture of the molecule Irganox 1010 in four, three, two or one parts, which correspond to molecules numbers 23, 24, 25 and 26 respectively.

3.1.2.2. Family 2: With glycerol molecule

The next group comprised the compounds with structures with glycerol. This group was divided into the compounds whose molecular formula were $C_xH_{2x}O_4$ (Table 2 from number 27 to 32) corresponding to an ester of an acid chain bonded to a glycerol molecule. And those compounds (table 2 from number 33 to 38) whose molecular formula was $C_xH_{2x-2}O_5$, where glycerol was bonded to two same ester chains. The difference of mass between the consecutive molecules was m/z 28.0298 that corresponds to the gain of C_2H_4 . Compounds from 39 to 41 did not form Na adducts. Their molecular structures responded to the formula, $C_xH_{2x-6}O_4$. They may be an ester of an acid but with three unsaturated hydrocarbon chains bonded to the glycerol molecule.

Only the compounds glyceryl monostearate, glyceryl palmitate and glyceryl dihexadecanoate were found as standards and they were corroborated by checking their retention times and their mass spectra. The mass fragments of the rest of compounds were similar to those obtained for the compounds 27 to 32 (Table 2) the common abundant fragments $[MNa^+]-2.9980$ m/z, $[MNa^+]-39.9925$ m/z (lost of Na adduct and OH) and $[MNa^+]-58.0702$. And for the compounds 33 to 38 (Table 2) $[MNa^+]-39.9925$ (lost of Na adduct and OH) and the mass fragment 239.1455.

It is known that the glyceryl monostearate (compound 8) is widely used as additive of anti-fog and anti-static additive in plastics [28, 42]. However, application of the rest of glycerol molecules is not known. Only the glyceryl monolaurate as antistatic plasticizer is known for PVC, PS and cellulosic plastics (that it was not the case under study) and glyceryl monopalmitate was found in bibliography as anti-foggy [6]. Therefore, the detection of these compounds in some samples can be related to the impurity of glyceryl monostearate as additive.

3.1.2.3. Family 3: Dihydroxy alquilamines

Family 3 consisted of dihydroxy alquilamines. This group was formed by the compounds from number 42 to 50 of Table 2. Their molecular formula responded to $C_xH_{2x+3}NO_2$ and its structure consisted of an amine bonded to two ethanol molecules and also an alkyl hydrocarbon chain. The mass difference between the consecutive compounds was m/z 14.023, which corresponded to the gain of CH_2 in the alkyl hydrocarbon chain.

The identification of compound number 44 was corroborated by the standard N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) dodecylamine which was commercially available, checking its retention time and its fragmentation profile.

Within this family, the smaller compound had a chain of eight carbons N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) octylamine and the bigger compound with twenty two carbons was N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) didodecylamine. Most of these compounds were formed with an even number of carbons in their alkyl hydrocarbon chains, except the compounds 45 and 47 that had thirteen and fifteen carbons respectively. Furthermore, it should be highlighted that these last two compounds were found in 15 samples of PP.

All these had the same fragmentation pattern, with common accurate masses such as 70.0646, 88.0768, 102.0903 and 106.0876 m/z . Besides of the most abundant fragment whose mass corresponded to $[MH^+] - 18.0088$ (m/z) ($[MH^+]-OH$).

In bibliography the presence of these migrants is attributed to a possible impurity/reaction product/breakdown product of the additives used. This consideration was obtained from FDA [33] or also found in bibliography like antistatic additive [28]

3.1.2.4. Family 4: Ceramide and Dihydroceramide

The family four was constituted by the compounds from 51 to 57 of Table 2. Ceramides are a family of waxy lipid molecules which are composed of sphingosine (an 18 carbon amino alcohol with an unsaturated hydrocarbon chain) and a fatty acid. They respond to the molecular formula $C_xH_{x-1}NO_3$. The difference between the dehydroceramide and ceramide molecules is that unsaturated hydrocarbon chain is substituted by saturated chain. Therefore, the hydroceramide molecules have two hydrogen atoms more in their formula, responding to $C_xH_{x+1}NO_3$ formula.

In the samples studied, only C20-ceramide (Table 2, compound 57) was detected. However six hydroceramides were found. Most of them were formed with odd number of carbons in their fatty acid chains (gaining a mass of m/z 28.0312 corresponding to C_2H_4) and only one with even carbon number (C16-dydroceramide, Table 2, compound 54). Due to the absence of any of these standards, they were checked by MassFragment[®] analysis and the mass spectrum obtained in the QTOF at high collision energy, where the fragmentation of these markers was similar to these candidates.

It is known, that some hydro-ceramides are widely used as a functional ingredient for cosmetics [45, 46], but nothing has been found about their presence in plastics. For this reason, they can be considered NIAS where its origin is unknown.

3.1.2.5. Family 5: Amides bonded by ethylene

Other group consisted of the compounds formed by two amides of the same acid bonded by ethylene (compounds from 58 to 62). These compounds formed sodium adducts $[MNa^+]$ and their molecular formula responded to $C_xH_{2x}N_2O_2$. The mass difference between the consecutive molecules was 28.0312 produced by the gain of C_2H_4 , It meant the presence of a methyl in each chain of amide.

Octadecanamide, N,N'-1,2-ethanediylbis- was confirmed with its standard by retention time and its spectrum. The most abundant masses found in their spectrum corresponded to the formation of Na-dimer and the common fragment $[M]+15.9949$ m/z (their oxidations)

Within this group, the biggest compound was Octadecanamide, N,N'-1,2-ethanediylbis-, which is a synthetic wax used as a dispersing agent or internal/external lubricant [47]. The application of the rest of compounds of this series was unknown, so it is not

unreasonable to think that they may be degradation products from this lubricant losing C₂H₄.

3.1.2.6. *Other compounds*

The last part of Table 2 contains other compounds. The most probable molecules for 63 and 64 (table 2), corroborated by Mass Fragment® analysis, were formed by an amine bonded to an ethanol, a methyl and also an alkyl hydrocarbon chains. Checking the results above described, it was found a great similarity between these ones and the family number 3, where an ethanol was substituted by a methyl.

The compounds 65 and 66 responded to [MH⁺] ionization and both compounds gave a mass difference of 28.0304 (gain C₂H₄), as before. Its molecular formula was C_xH_{2x+1}NO that would correspond to the amide family. Due to the absence of pure standards it was not possible to accurately identify both compounds but the most probable migrants according to MassFragment ® are shown in Table 2. The compounds 67 and 68, with formula C_xH_{x-3}NO and mass difference between both also of 28.0317 m/z (gain of C₂H₄), were dimethyl and diethyl of linoleamide respectively as the most probable molecules.

The compounds 69 and 70 were confirmed with their standards.

Other three compounds (71, 72 and 73) with C_xH_{x+1}NO as molecular formula were detected whose mass difference was also 28.0312 m/z (gain of C₂H₄). In this case, they would be primary amides corroborated by their fragmentations with the standard octadecanamide obtaining the same fragmentation pattern with the common fragment masses 293.2844, 292.3001 and 275.2739 m/z.

All these amides above described could come from the impurities or degradation products from erucamide and oleamide widely used as slip agents [42].

Finally, the compound 74, that appeared in almost of samples, and whose molecular formula was C₄₂H₆₃O₄P, corresponded to the gain of an oxygen regarding irgafos 168 (C₄₂H₆₃O₃P). To corroborate its identification, 10ppm of irgafos 168 standard was oxidized with tetrahydrofuran during 1day at 40°C in an oven [48] and analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF. The chromatographic peak of irgafos 168 disappeared and a new

peak appeared at the same time and mass fragmentation as compound 74, confirming that it is the oxo-derivative from irgafos 168.

3.2. *Quantification of migrants.*

Once all migrant compounds were identified, the migration concentrations were quantified in each simulant. Table 4 shows the commercial standards used, their limits of detection and quantification and its reproducibility. It is also detailed what standard was used to quantify the compounds identified whose compound was not commercial available.

As can be seen, good results were obtained in terms of detection and quantification limits, linearity and reproducibility. The LOD values were between 10 $\mu\text{g/Kg}$, for most of the compounds, and 240 $\mu\text{g/Kg}$ (Palmitic and stearic acid) which were detected in negative mode, where the ionization was less sensitive.

Considering the high number of compounds identified, and the great number of migration values obtained by twenty six samples studied in at least three simulants, we decided to use a principal component analysis (PCA) performed with Unscrambler v.9.7. to facilitate the interpretation of data.

Figure 3 shows the score plots (left graphics) and correlation loadings plots (right graphics) for the different simulants used. The correlation in all cases is very high with values of accumulated variance between 71% and 99%.

For ethanol 95% used as food simulant, when the results were plotted as scores (graphic 1, left), 3 groups of samples were differentiated. The group 1 included the samples PP19, PP20 and PP11 where the highest migration values of glyceryl monostearate obtained (between 14.5 ± 0.8 and 33.3 ± 1.2 mg/ Kg of simulant) were discriminated for this group. This fact was represented in the correlation loadings plot (right) where the compound 7 was located near the border. The group 2 was constituted by the samples PP5 and PP15 which had the highest values of erucamide migration (compound 12) 24.1 ± 1.7 and 38.3 ± 2.1 mg / Kg of simulant respectively. Other discriminatory migration values for this group were the migration of the even dihydroxy alquilamines (42, 43, 44,

46, 48, 49 and 59) and some ceramides (54 and 57) shown in graphic 1, at right. The rest PPs were grouped in group 3.

The score and correlation loadings plots obtained for the simulants ethanol 10% and acetic 3% were very similar. In both cases, the values of migration were the lowest compared to other simulants and closer between these ones. As shows Figure 3 (Graphics 2 and 3, left) the samples are plotted together in 4 groups. The first one was formed by the samples PP6 and PP7 characterized by the highest values of odd dihydroxy alquilamines for these simulants (compounds 45 and 47 in graphics 2 and 3, left). Values were between 0.07 ± 0.01 and 2.25 ± 0.33 mg/ Kg of simulant. The second group was constituted by the samples PP3 and PP9, they were also discriminated by the migration of these odd dihydroxy alquilamines (compounds 45 and 47), with values lower than those mentioned above and between 0.04 ± 0.01 and 1.21 ± 0.06 mg/ Kg of simulant. The group 3 only consisted of sample PP5 whose migration values of even dihydroxy alquilamines were the highest shown in the graphics 2 and 3, right, with values between 0.07 ± 0.01 and 5.41 ± 0.33 . The rest of PPs were within the group 4.

Finally, the graphics 4 expressed the score and correlation loadings plots obtained for Tenax. Three groups of samples were constituted for this simulant. In the first one, the samples PP 16 and 18 were grouped due to their highest and discriminatory migration values of compounds glyceryl monopalmitate and both odd hydroxyamides (compounds 29, 45 and 47 showed graphic 4, right). Also some glyceryl compounds (28, 32, 33 and 37) and the break-down product as ethyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoate (20) were characteristic of these samples. On the other hand, the samples PP11, PP19 and PP20 were together in group 2 with the highest migration values of glyceryl monostearate (7) as occurred for ethanol 95%.

3.3. Risk assessment.

In order to apply the risk assessment to these polymers, all values of migration were compared to their SML (10/2011/EU [13]) or to the maximum values according by Cramer for those non listed compounds in the EU regulation 10/2011/EU.

Thirty three compounds appeared in the legislation 10/2011/EU: oleamide, erucamide, irganox 1010, irgafos 168, palmitic and stearic acid, hexa-octa-decanamide N,N'-1,2-ethanediylbis-, 11-Eicosenamide, (11Z) and the family 2 called “with glycerol molecule” and all of them are authorized without SML. The family 3 called “dyhydroxy alquilamines” have SML expressed as group where the sum of the compounds [N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) (C8-C18) amine] must not exceed 1.2 mg/Kg. However, the samples PP5, PP6 and PP7 didn't comply with the legislation for none simulant as these compounds surpass this limit. Also PP11 for ethanol 95% and PP3 for ethanol 95% and acetic 3% exceeded this SML.

Other compounds like NX8000 , Irganox 3114 and Irganox 1076 had a SML of 5, 5 and 6 mg/Kg respectively. The NX8000 and Irganox 3114 concentrations were below their specific migration limit in all samples. However, Irganox 1076 was found in the sample PP25 with a concentration of 10.2 ± 1.85 mg/Kg for ethanol 95% surpassing its SML (6mg/Kg).

Concerning the non-listed compounds in the positive list of the legislation 10/2011/EU, their concentrations were compared with the maximum values according by Cramer classes. Six samples overcame the maximum concentration recommended by Cramer for the simulant ethanol 95%. PP25 due to the compound of Class II, hexyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoate with a concentration of 4.19 ± 0.06 mg/Kg . And benzenepropanoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, 1,1'-[2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediyl] ester and Benzenepropanoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, 1,1'-[2-[[3-[3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]-1-oxopropoxy]methyl]-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediyl] ester with concentrations of 2.05 ± 0.22 and 0.89 ± 0.03 for sample PP26. The samples PP5, PP10, PP11 and PP15 didn't comply with Cramer limits for different types compounds of Class III such as the group of dihydroceramides and Tetra-penta and heptadecanamide,N,N'-1,2-ethanediylbis- in ethanol 95% as simulant, although they complied for the aqueous simulants.

4. Conclusions

Non-volatile migrants from twenty six PP films to be used as food packaging materials have been identified and quantified. The study has been carried out using UPLC/MS/QTOF, which has demonstrated to be a powerful technique for the elucidation of unknown compounds, based on the possibility of obtaining the accurate mass of precursor and their fragment ions. A total of seventy five compounds were identified. Sixteen were additives like antioxidants, plasticizers, lubricants...and the rest, fifty seven, were NIAS. They could come from rupture of these additives due to their similar structures, like derivatives of Irganox 1010 and 1076 or the group of glycerol molecules. Also impurities, as N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) amines, or compounds of unknown origin, like hydro-ceramides. These results reinforced the necessity of analyzing in depth the migration sample after exposure in order to identify the NIAS compounds.

The quantification of these identified compounds has been carried out at low detection limits around 10 ppb. The results of the migration assays showed that 35% of the films didn't comply, six of these exceeded the SML for European legislation 10/2011/EU [13] (five samples due to group N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) amine and one sample due to Irganox 1076). Six samples overcame the maximum concentration recommended by Cramer for the compound hexyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoate derivative of Irganox 1010 and 1076 among others.

And finally, despite the complexity of NIAS identification, this work provides a lot of new compounds that could be important for future works. And also, it opens up a wide range of possibilities for the plastic manufactured companies that can reformulate and substitute some additives which are related with these NIAS found.

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